

A STUDY ON EXPLORING THE UNCONVENTIONAL SYSTEM OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This project is about education and incorporation of traditional system of education in our formal system with a focus on the instructional relevance of local cultural resource knowledge such as the relevance of traditional customs and practices. Using an exhaustive questionnaire, the project examines the knowledge of students, teachers and parents on indigenous system, their view point of incorporating modern and traditional system of education and the level of sustainability of such a system. The data analysis reveals that 69% of people think that indigenous system of education is a practical system and 79% think that it can prepare students for a better future. The survey makes it very clear that most of the people (97%) are of the view point that indigenous system is a value based system of education. When it comes to the acceptability of traditional system of education, 85% of the people are willing to go in for this system of education and 94% think that formal and indigenous systems can be integrated. Considering the acceptability level of this system of education, the project has been designed to suggest ways for successful and practical ways of imparting knowledge of traditional practices to the present generation, by incorporating the chapters related to the same in science curriculum. The main focus of the project has been to acquaint the present generation to their traditions and cultural practices. To fulfil the aim, stress has been laid on learning by doing and hence suggested curriculum mainly involves practicals, workshops and field trips which can prove to be helpful to the students. Learners can be assisted to integrate values and ideas that have proven to work effectively in the education of youth in their own culture and cultural practices.

Key words: Learning, Unconventional, traditional system, Education